

Competency needs for interoperability in digital twins data spaces applied to cities

Within the framework of the European Strategy for a Data Economy, data spaces are becoming established as key infrastructures for facilitating the secure, governed and interoperable exchange of data between multiple actors. However, their success does not depend solely on technology, but also on human capabilities to design, implement and maintain standards, semantic models and governance agreements.

This questionnaire is part of the work of the **DIS4SME** project and aims to identify the roles, knowledge and skills needed to advance interoperability within data spaces, with a focus on spatial data and urban digital twins. The results will help design training pathways, micro-credentials and training programmes that are more aligned with the real needs of professionals, public administrations and businesses. Participation is voluntary and anonymous.

The estimated time to complete the questionnaire is 2 to 5 minutes. If you are involved in projects related to urban data, digital twins or interoperability, your experience will be particularly valuable.

Thank you for your collaboration!

Respondent Context

1. **Select the typology of organisation you belong to (select one): ***

- National Public Administration
- Local/Regional Administration
- Private company
- Small medium enterprise
- Large enterprise
- University / research centre
- NGO / professional association
- Other

2. Primary role of your company in the data ecosystem (select one or more) *

- Data provider (urban sensors, BIM models, cadastre, GIS, etc.)
- Infrastructure designer / data architect
- Technical operator (connectors, brokers, data platforms)
- Urban planning or smart city manager
- Digital twin or GIS-BIM project manager
- Policy-maker / public regulator
- Data provider/user (analyst, consultant, developer)
- Research
- Standardization body
- Other

3. Main area of action (select one or more): *

- Urban or territorial planning
- Agriculture
- Smart cities (mobility, energy, water, climate, etc.)
- Construction and infrastructure (BIM, GIS-BIM)
- Local or regional public administration
- Projects
- Digital twin pilots
- Other

Participating organization Information

4. Your Age *

- Less than 20
- 20 - 29
- 30 - 39
- 40 - 49
- 50 - 59
- More than 59

5. Select your role within your organisation (Select your role within your organisation) *

- Manager
- Technician
- Researcher
- Policymaker
- Other

6. Which is your country?

Participant knowledge/expertise

7. What data activities do you perform or coordinate in your organisation (select all that apply)? *

	Yes	No	I don't know
Secure data access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data Cataloguing and publication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data transformation and harmonisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data Integration from different sources	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality validation / standard compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Definition or use of semantic models (ontologies, vocabularies)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Traceability / logging / data lineage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data usage agreements / contracts / policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. Other data-related activities carried out or coordinated within your organisation

Functions and knowledge linked to Data Spaces

9. What is the level of knowledge you have on data space or digital twins? *

	High	Medium	Under	Null	Not applicable
Your knowledge on data space	<input type="radio"/>				
Your knowledge on digital twins space	<input type="radio"/>				

10. Are you currently involved in any projects related to data spaces or digital twins?

11. What technical or management activities do you or your team perform regarding urban data/digital twins? (Select all that apply) *

- Data Access (from heterogeneous sources)
- Cataloguing and publication data (metadata, DCAT)
- Data transformation and harmonization (ETL, APIs, vocabularies)
- Use of semantic models (ontologies, data alignment)
- Ensuring traceability and data lineage (logging, versioning)
- Define usage agreements and exchange conditions
- Not any
- Other

12. **What technical or management activities do you or your team perform regarding data space?**

(Select all that apply) *

- Data sharing with third parties (connectors, brokers)
- Define usage agreements and exchange conditions
- Orchestrating data flows in a data space
- Not any
- Other

13. **What is the level of knowledge you (or your team) currently have for these activities? ***

	High	Medium	Under	Null	Not applicable
Data access Data	<input type="radio"/>				
Cataloguing and publication	<input type="radio"/>				
Data transformation and harmonization	<input type="radio"/>				
Semantic modeling	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of standards (DCAT, OGC API, Open BIM...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Implementation of connectors (IDSA...)	<input type="radio"/>				

14. **For the Data Access (from heterogeneous sources) activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Standard data model (INSPIRE)
- OGC standards
- Open BIM
- Formats and protocols for data exchange (e.g., ISO/IEC 11179, ISO 19115, W3C standards)
- JSON, XML, CSV, RDF,IFC
- APIs and data access protocols
- Not any
- Other

15. **For the data Cataloguing and publication activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Metadata standards (DCAT, Dublin Core, ISO19115))
- Data Discovery and Cataloguing Tools (CKAN, DataHub, Amundsen, Apache Atlas)
- Data catalog integration (API,...)
- Standards for Data Publication (FAIR, LOD, Open Data)
- Not any
- Other

16. **For the Data transformation and harmonization activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Data mapping from differed sources
- Data modeling (JSON, GeoJSON, XML)
- Not any
- Other

17. **For the semantic modelling activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Knowledge of sectorial ontologies
- Use of standard vocabularies
- Linked data
- Not any
- Other

18. **For the Data sharing with third parties activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Connectors
- Brokers
- Not any
- Other

19. **For the Ensuring traceability and data lineage activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Data Lineage Tools & Frameworks
- Logging and Monitoring Systems
- Knowledge of Database Formats and Metadata Technologies
- Not any
- Other

20. **For the Define usage agreements and exchange conditions activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Data Governance Act, Data Act, Open Data Directive
- GDPR
- Licensing and rights management (es. Creative Commons)
- Not any
- Other

21. **For the Orchestrating data flows in a data space activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?**

(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below) *

- Data Integration & ETL/ELT
- Workflow Orchestration Tool
- APIs and Data Services
- Federated Data Access
- Not any
- Other

22. **What type of skills do you consider to be the most difficult to find or fill in your organisation? (Select up to 3) ***

- Data Cataloguing and publication
- Data transformation and harmonization
- Semantic modelling
- Data sharing with third parties
- Ensuring traceability and data lineage
- Define usage agreements and exchange conditions
- Orchestrating data flows in a data space
- Not any
- Other

23. **Which of the following training course formats do you consider most useful for improving these competences? ***

- Online technical courses (self-training)
- Webinar
- Hands-on Practical workshops with real use cases
- On-the-job training (internal mentoring)
- Short guidelines or explanatory videos
- Not any
- Other

24. Which kind of certification would you like to be provided? *

- Certificate of Attendance
- Certificate of Achievement
- Official or regulated national certification
- European micro-credentials
- I do not need certification
- Not any
- Other

Level of maturity of the data space and future needs

25. **Which best describes the current state of the data space in which your organisation participates?**
(Choose the one that comes closest) *

- Level 0- We haven't started yet.
- Level 1 - Isolated: Data management is local, not interoperable. No exchange mechanisms.
- Level 2 - Connected: There are APIs or open formats for sharing data, but no common semantics or clear rules.
- Level 3 - Interoperable: Standards are applied (DCAT, NGSI-LD, AAS...), there is exchange with third parties and basic governance.
- Level 4 - Federated: We actively participate in an interoperable data space, with trust agreements and shared services.
- Level 5 - Ecosystemic: We interoperate with other data spaces, share AI models and advanced governance.
- Other

26. **What challenges do you foresee in the next 2 years to advance to the next level?**
(Select up to 3) *

- Lack of staff with interoperability skills
- Need to align with semantic standards
- Difficulty integrating BIM/GIS data with urban services
- Lack of clear governance and access rules
- Difficulty in using common connectors or infrastructures (IDSA, Simpl...)
- Need to integrate AI or simulation models (advanced digital twins)
- Not any
- Other

27. What additional expertise do you see as key to improving the maturity of data space? *

- Advanced semantic modelling (ontologies, SHACL, common vocabularies)
- Reference Architectures (IDS-RAM, GAIA-X, DSSC blueprint)
- Heterogeneous urban data integration (IoT, BIM, GIS, cadastral databases)
- Designing contracts and data use policies
- Interoperability between sectoral data spaces
- Distributed data governance
- Automation of validation and quality control flows
- Not any
- Other

28. Would you be interested in participating in pilot initiatives or co-creation groups to develop these capacities? *

- Yes, in cooperation with other cities / regions
- Yes, within my own organisation
- No, for the moment

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